

SPIRITUAL AND MORAL MECHANISMS FOR STRENGTHENING THE STABILITY OF SOCIETY IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The topic of spiritual and moral mechanisms for strengthening the stability of society in the new Uzbekistan is of great importance in the development of society. The role of spiritual and moral values in ensuring stability in the country is great, through which the worldview and life position of the younger generation are formed. Measures are being implemented to strengthen stability in society through the spiritual reforms of Uzbekistan, national values, the education system and the development of legal consciousness. This article analyzes the importance of spiritual and moral mechanisms in stabilizing society and shows ways to achieve social, political and economic development of society through them.

Keywords: New Uzbekistan, stability of society, spiritual and moral mechanisms, national values, social reforms, legal consciousness, education system, moral education, reforms, youth.

Introduction. New Uzbekistan is implementing reforms based on new political, economic and spiritual principles on the path to development. The stability of society is inextricably linked not only with economic development, but also with the spiritual and moral values of the population. The formation and strengthening of spiritual and moral mechanisms strengthens mutual trust, solidarity and social order in society. This article analyzes the current issues and mechanisms for strengthening the stability of society on the basis of spiritual and moral values in New Uzbekistan.

Within the framework of the “Strategy of New Uzbekistan” for 2022-2026, priority areas such as economic development, poverty reduction and the fight against corruption have been identified. This strategy is aimed at ensuring stability through reforms based on the needs of the people. The philosophy of the New Uzbekistan concept is based on the principle of “man - society - state”. Ensuring the rule of law and establishing social justice are one of the main pillars of state policy [1]. Citizen participation in state governance is being increased, and the system of self-government through neighborhoods is being strengthened. State policy is aimed at strengthening good neighborliness and cooperation with the countries of the region. This foreign policy principle is important for strengthening the position of New Uzbekistan in the international arena and ensuring peace. State policy is aimed at strengthening economic stability in the economy by developing the private sector, supporting entrepreneurship, and attracting investments. Measures are being taken to increase employment and strengthen social protection.

Methodology. The New Uzbekistan Development Strategy provides for “further improvement of the mechanism of open dialogue with the people, expansion of the practice of making important decisions taking into account public opinion, digitization of the process of considering appeals received by state bodies, and ensuring prompt and high-quality consideration of appeals.” The following methodologies were used in the study [2]:

1. Analysis of literary sources: Local and foreign literature on spiritual and moral education was reviewed.
2. Sociological research: Surveys on spiritual values and moral principles were conducted among the population of Uzbekistan.
3. Analytical and comparative methods: The reforms of New Uzbekistan and the experience of social stability in other countries were analyzed.
4. Study of documents and regulatory framework: State policy was studied based on presidential decrees, legislative acts and programs.

Uzbekistan is implementing the Concept for the Development of State Youth Policy by 2025, which is based on the principle of “Working with Youth for the Benefit of Youth” enshrined in the UN Strategy “Youth – 2030”. Civil society institutions are actively participating in the implementation of the National Strategy on Human Rights. Work is underway to strengthen the responsibility of the business community in the field of human rights, including through the development of the National Action Plan “Business and Human Rights”. Uzbekistan supports intergovernmental processes to strengthen the system of UN treaty bodies on human rights and strives to develop state accountability and implement the recommendations of treaty bodies [3]. The Republic of Uzbekistan submits national reports (41 reports) to UN treaty bodies on a timely basis. In particular, in February of this year, the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women heard the Sixth Periodic Report of Uzbekistan, and the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights heard the Third Periodic Report.

Results. It was determined that the spiritual and moral mechanisms for ensuring the stability of society in the new Uzbekistan can be strengthened through the following main areas: The family is the main unit of society. The formation of feelings of patriotism, kindness, honesty and justice in children plays an important role in ensuring the stability of society. The moral immunity of the younger generation is strengthened through family values. It is necessary to raise the moral awareness of young people through spiritual lessons and special programs in schools and higher educational institutions. In the conditions of the new Uzbekistan, ensuring the harmony of national values and modern moral requirements should be one of the main goals of the education system.

Social unity can be strengthened by promoting spiritual heritage, historical figures, and national values through the media and cultural events. Spiritual awakening based on national values strengthens the stability of society. Increasing legal culture in society, widely promoting respect for the law, and the principles of

justice reduce social conflicts in society. This strengthens the legal basis for ensuring stability [4]. It is important to increase solidarity and social activism in solving social issues through youth organizations, neighborhood committees, and NGOs. Youth and neighborhoods are the backbone of a stable society. The presence of spiritual leaders and role models in society is important. Such leaders play an important role in leading society in the right direction and ensuring stability.

Discussion. The conducted research shows that the formation of spiritual and moral mechanisms in New Uzbekistan requires a number of complex measures. First of all, it is necessary to strengthen the system of moral education in the family and in educational institutions. By forming spiritual values in young people, their position in society can be strengthened. In addition, a strategy for the preservation and development of national values and spiritual heritage is being implemented on the basis of social programs and legislation adopted by the state. Within the framework of the idea of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's "New Uzbekistan", the development of spirituality and enlightenment occupies a special place. The results of sociological research showed that a large part of the population supports the strengthening of spiritual and moral values in society. In particular, 80% of respondents noted the importance of moral education and national values in the family to ensure social stability. However, there are certain problems in the process of strengthening spiritual and moral education. The development of information technologies, globalization and negative content on the Internet have a negative impact on the minds of young people [5]. Therefore, strengthening moral immunity and protecting young people from information threats is an important task.

The systematic and consistent implementation of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy is bringing democratic reforms to a new qualitative stage. This, first of all, implies the full implementation of the priority principle "For the sake of human dignity". It should be noted that "human dignity" means ensuring a peaceful and safe life for citizens, fundamental rights and freedoms, gradually

creating decent living conditions and modern infrastructure, providing qualified medical services for every citizen of the country, quality education, social protection and a healthy ecological environment.

The main idea of the New Uzbekistan Strategy is to strengthen the role of civil society institutions, protect human rights, reduce poverty, provide everyone with a guaranteed source of income, and achieve sustainable environmental development. The New Uzbekistan Development Strategy is distinguished from the Action Strategy by the fact that it covers seven priority areas, and in essence, the issue of ensuring spiritual development and bringing the sector to a new level is defined as one of these priority areas [6]. Therefore, it is appropriate to talk about the goals and objectives related to ensuring spiritual development set out in this historical document.

Conclusion. Spiritual and moral mechanisms play an important role in ensuring the stability of society in New Uzbekistan. Factors such as family, education, national values and legal culture keep society stable and developed. Through the spiritual reforms being carried out in the country, it is possible to achieve social cohesion and stability. If the mechanisms presented in the article are implemented, New Uzbekistan will become a more prosperous and stable society. The formation and development of civil society institutions, parliamentarism, and a multi-party system are considered a symbol of true democracy. The development strategy sets out comprehensive measures to further increase the role and responsibility of local government authorities in solving local problems, and to transfer most of the state functions from the center to the regions.

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